

RESEARCH OF IMPACT TEST BASED ON ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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ABSTRACT

Impact test is an important item of the plane for the first flying. Acoustic Emission (AE) characteristics could reflect the process of structure damage and location. Aiming at calculating the monitoring probability of the impact damage and the location reliability based on AE, impact tests on a composite wing box were carried out. Firstly, AE characteristics were utilized to analysis structure damages, and calculate the monitoring probability of impact damages based on Bayes theory. Secondly, for 2D location, the error of composite structure damage location was researched. Results indicate that AE could predict the structural damages, this research could give reference for the monitoring probability of discrete element impact test on composite structures, and analysis for the damage source locations.

1 INTRODUCTION

The advance of the aircraft structural damage tolerance design principle negates the old design principle which only depends on the structural design to guarantee the aircraft safety, and the significance of damage detection is emphasize^[1]. Structural damages should be detected and obtain maintenance before structural residual strength falls down to the prescriptive value, which desired by damage tolerance design of airplane, thus nondestructive inspection exerts important function in aircraft structure safety.

Impact test is an important item of the plane for its first flying. While Acoustic Emission (AE) characteristics could reflect the process of structure damage and location. There have been many applications on the aircraft detections using AE. M. Surgeon etc^[2] researched the AE signal of SiC /BMA composite laminate under stretching effect, described the damage and fracture mechanism of the composite laminate. Geng Rongsheng etc^[3] have already actualized AE real-time monitoring of damages for central wing and outer panel jointing area during full-scale aircraft body fatigue test successfully. Wang Bingyang etc^[4] accomplished the damage monitoring for the main landing gear beam during its fatigue test using trend analysis. Probability of Crack Detection curve is the main approach to express the reliability of nondestructive inspection. Scholars have done a lot of research^[5-6], Liu Xiuli etc compiled the handbook of POD for crack damage after a lot analysis of the normal detection methods^[7]. While AE detection in composite material was not contained in this handbook.

The veracity of the AE location reflects the accordance between detection location and the real damage location. Many experiments and equipments applied the time difference method for positioning^[8]. However, affected by the environment and test material, the positioning result always appears errors. At present, the monitoring reliability research of damage based on AE is less. It is urgent and important to carry out the reliability research of structural damage location based on AE.

Thus, Aiming at calculating the monitoring probability of the impact damage and the location reliability based on AE, an impact test research on a composite wing box was carried out in combination with piezoelectric technology.

2 STATISTIC METHOD OF MONITORING MONITORING DATA BASED ON RELIABILITY

Monitoring reliability calculation by AE technique should solve the following issues: a. turn the target into mathematics problem; b. how to determine the monitoring times; c. how to estimate the damage detection probability based on the monitoring data.

2.1 Turn to mathematics problem

Monitoring event A is assumed to undergo repeated independent detection of n times, the probability of event A occurring is p (unknown) in each monitoring. If event A occurs r times totally in the n times tests, r asymptotically obeys normal distribution $N(np, (\sqrt{np(1-p)})^2)$ based on probability theory. Thus,

$$U = \frac{r - np}{\sqrt{np(1-p)}} = \frac{r/n - p}{\sqrt{p(1-p)/n}} \sim N(0,1)$$

2.2 Detection times calculation^[9]

There are only “detected” and “undetected” two results in impact damage inspection, which obeys the binomial distribution. In order to estimate the damage forecast probability p_i in detection test correctly, the confidence $1-\alpha$ for one-sided confidence interval is presented in following equation.

$$P\{U > u_\alpha\} = \alpha$$

Owing to take the confidence lower limit (or upper limit) into account scarcely, the upper bound of distribution could be considered as $+\infty$ (or zero), hence there is:

$$P\left\{\frac{r/n - p}{\sqrt{p(1-p)/n}} \leq u_\alpha\right\} = 1 - \alpha$$

Namely

$$p > \frac{r}{n} - u_\alpha \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}}$$

The confidence upper limit of p could be calculated alike:

$$p < \frac{r}{n} + u_\alpha \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}}$$

Thus the one-sided confidence interval estimate of the collectivity ratio p is $[0, \frac{r}{n} + u_\alpha \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}}]$

or $[\frac{r}{n} - u_\alpha \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}}, 1]$.

The one-way deviation allowance ε could be calculated as

$$\varepsilon = u_\alpha \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}}$$

Then

$$n = \frac{u_\alpha^2 p(1-p)}{\varepsilon^2} \quad (1)$$

In the case of determining one-way deviation allowance ε , the sample capacity of ratio estimation could be determined using Formula (1), that is the needed minimum independent inspecting times n_{min} , which lead the collectivity ratio p included in the interval $(0, \hat{p} + \varepsilon)$ or $(\hat{p} - \varepsilon, 1)$ at a given confidence level $1-\alpha$.

Where, the probability p could be derived by two methods: a. if there is historical data, use the approximation of p instead of p ; b. otherwise, set $p=0.5$ approximatively.

2.3 Bayesian estimation of the crack forecast probability $p^{[10]}$

For binomial distribution $B(1, p)$, suppose monitoring results $(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n)$ is the sample, coming from collectivity in which there are m "one", and

$$\xi_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{damage detected in } i_{st} \text{ inspection} \\ 0 & \text{damage undetected in } i_{st} \text{ inspection} \end{cases} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,n)$$

Interval estimation of the probability p could be calculated using mathematical statistics in confidence $1-\alpha$.

$$\left(\frac{m}{n} - u_{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \frac{m}{n} (1 - \frac{m}{n})}, \frac{m}{n} + u_{\frac{\alpha}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \frac{m}{n} (1 - \frac{m}{n})} \right) \quad (2)$$

If uniform distribution $R[0, 1]$ is predicted as prior distribution of probability p , the point estimation and maximum likelihood estimation of p is:

$$\hat{p} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (3)$$

For monitoring results $\xi \sim B(1, p)$, the united probability function of $(\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n)$ is:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n p^{\xi_i} (1-p)^{1-\xi_i} = p^{\sum x_i} (1-p)^{n-\sum x_i}$$

Then, posterior distribution density could be derived:

$$h(p | x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{P^{\sum x_i} (1-P)^{n-\sum x_i}}{B(\sum x_i + 1, n + 1 - \sum x_i)} \quad (4)$$

Where, $0 \leq p \leq 1$.

Considering the united probability function and posterior distribution density of $(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi_3, \dots, \xi_n)$, the Bayes estimation of probability p is:

$$\hat{p} = \int_0^1 p h(p | x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) dp = \frac{1 + \sum x_i}{n + 2} \quad (5)$$

Where, $x_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{crack appears in } i_{st} \text{ inspection} \\ 0 & \text{crack doesn't appear in } i_{st} \text{ inspection} \end{cases} (i=1,2,\dots,n)$

2.4 Damage source location error

Judge the abnormality AE signal and locate the damage using two-dimensional plane location, Position accuracy depends on two points: one is the correct set of sound velocity, the other is the judge standard. For example, if the location judge standard is set that the predicted position of AE location is within the 1.2 times radius of the actual impact damage area, the predicted positioning could be considered correct. (Actual damage area is determined by NDT.) Diagnostic tests are carried out for health monitoring and damage location. Take the collected positioning signals as samples. If locate correctly, $p=1$, otherwise, $p=0$, it obeys the binomial distribution, so hypothesis is considered to accomplish the statistic and analysis of location error.

When impact tests are carried out n times with damages identified successfully r times, hypothesis $H_0: p < p_0$, could be set with a certain significance level α . That is:

$$P\{r > r_\alpha\} \leq \alpha$$

If $r \leq r_\alpha$, consider the damage location index meet the $p < p_0$ requirement. Where, the test time n could be determined by damage detection probability calculation.

3 AE DETECTION FOR IMPACT TEST

3.1 Monitoring equipment

The monitoring equipment used AE system from PAC, including signal select instrument, sensors (resonant frequency 150 KHz), preamplifier, etc. The process of AE resonant frequency signal collection was shown in figure 1. Simultaneously, equip with Smart Composite piezoelectric damage monitoring system.

Figure 1: The process of AE signal collection

Impact test was carried out on drop hammer impact device, the hammer weight was 0.5Kg~20Kg, and impact energy was selected between 1J~150J. According to the test requirement, different energies were chosen to carry out drop hammer impact, and selected IMC-IV impact control instrument, whose frequency precision was 6.4×10^{-6} .

3.2 Test steps

Firstly, test piece. Impact tests were carried out on a composite box whose lower wing panel was multi-spar integral molding composite structure. The size of the box was 900mm×501mm×110mm, other parts and upside of the box were aluminum.

Secondly, sensor layout. The sensors were mainly laid on the lower wing panel of the composite box for mainly assess its impact load resistance. There were fourteen AE sensors totally, which composed four groups of two-dimensional plane location, seen in Figure 2. Simultaneously, lay out piezoelectric sensors reasonably on corresponding impact locations for piezoelectric damage complementarity monitoring. In this test, correct calibration and sound velocity needed to be set carefully for each plane monitoring array because of inner vertical-spar and angle section in the composite box.

Figure 2: AE sensors layout

Thirdly, set location group and collection equipment parameters reasonably. Due to the anisotropy of sound velocity in composite structures, two-dimensional plane location needed three sensors at least. However, three sensors location might engender a bogus AE source, four sensors array was used to locate the damage (seen in Figure 2). Set four location groups, planned impact pots A1~A2、C1~C2 lied in location group ①, and A3~A4, B1~B2, D1~D2 lied in location group ②, B4 lied in group ③, B3 lied in group ④. From Figure 2, set event definition value, event atresia value and excess location value etc for different location groups separately. Other AE collection parameters were set and shown in Table 1. The sound velocity was calculated before each monitoring test for every specimen, and finished the sensors calibration, other AE parameters held invariable, for the sake of consistency of the test monitoring.

Amplitude threshold /dB	Preamplifier gain /dB	Peak value / μ s	Time / μ s	Event time / μ s	Atresiatime / μ s
45	40	50		200	300

Table 1: AE collection parameters set

Fourthly, impact test. NDT was carried out to find the initial damage of the whole composite lower wing panel before test. While during the test, use AE and piezoelectric systems for real-time monitoring. AE parameters, such as amplitude, energy, counts, etc were selected to describe the AE signals. For each impact, implement A-scan on the impact area and determine the damage dimension.

4 STATISTICS AND ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT TEST MONITORING

4.1 Impact test

Select a sensor as the coordinate to locate the AE source for each two-dimensional plane location. The monitoring data were analyzed based on Matlab, if the distance L between actual damage area centroid and AE monitoring location $<$ actual damage radius $\times 1.2$, consider location correct, and mark 1. Otherwise, consider location false, mark 0. Take impact position A1 for example, the AE and piezoelectric signals were shown in Figure 3 to Figure 6.

(a) Energy 5J

(b) Energy 10J

Figure 3: AE location coordinate (Position A1)

(a) Energy 5J

(b) Energy 10J

Figure 4: Waveform of AE event (Position A1)

Figure 5: Piezoelectric damage monitoring of two impact tests (Position A1)

Figure 6 The relative positions between actual damage and piezoelectric location of A1

In Figure 6, the red parts were actual damage areas which determined by A-scan, while the black pots were the piezoelectric damage imaging coordinates. From Figure 6, it could be seen that the two damage location results both satisfied the index.

Figure 7: Actual impact test (Position A2)

The monitoring results indicated that AE could predict the impact damage effectively through the signal characteristic parameter analysis. When the sound velocity was set correctly, two-dimensional plane location had good performance. And AE combined with piezoelectric technology, they could complement each other and finish the impact damage judgment and location effectively.

4.2 damage monitoring probability

Utilizing Formula (1), select $p=0.5$, in the condition of 90% confidence level and 0.15 one-way deviation allowance, the needed independent minimum test times to calculate impact test monitoring actually, in which 21 times were effective, and detected damages 20 times. The impact damage monitoring results were shown in Table 2, where x_i expresses damage detection successfully and location, “detected”, mark “1”, “undetected”, mark “0”, the detection probability was expressed using p .

Impact serial number	Impact location	Impact energy	Damage radius /mm	Damage area dimension /mm ²	Monitoring results x_i
1	A1	5J	6	12×9	1
2	A1	10J	13	25×24	1
...
20	C2	5J	17	34×32	Invalidation
21	D1	8J	12	19×23	1
22	D2	8J	14	20×28	1
Σ					20

Table 2: Impact damage monitoring results

Based on the discussion in section 1, there are only “detected” and “undetected” two results in impact damage inspection, whose collectivity X obeys the two-point distribution $B(1, p)$. And the all impact times n was 21 in this research, detected damage event times r was 20, thus the Bayes estimate of AE monitoring probability p could be calculated using Formula (5) in the condition of 90% confidence level and 0.15 one-way deviation allowance.

$$p = \frac{1 + nx}{n + 2} \times 100\% = 91.304\% > 90\%$$

4.3 Impact location error research

According to the foregoing discussion, in this impact test, impact 22 times, detect and locate damage successfully 18 times. With $\alpha=0.1$ as significance level, $n=21$, $r=20$, $p_0=0.8$, and p_0 is the minimum value which p should satisfy. Thus, the observation ratio was

$$\frac{r}{n} = 0.9523 > p_0 = 0.8$$

According to the method discussed in section 1.4:

$$Q(n, r, p_0) = \sum_{k=r}^n C_n^k p_0^k (1 - p_0)^{n-k} = 0.0576 < \alpha = 0.1$$

So reject null hypothesis $H_0: p < 0.8$.

Namely, the location error rate of damage events was no less than 80% with $\alpha=0.1$ as significance level in this impact test, that is location error was less than 20%, which satisfied the demand.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, impact tests were carried out and results were analyzed to identify the composite material damage and calculate the monitoring probability in multi-spar integral molding composite structure using AE signal amplitude and other parameter as characteristic, the damage location of AE monitoring combined with piezoelectric technology was researched. Main findings could be summarized as follows:

- According the statistic analysis of the monitoring signal data, the correct prediction for damage was calculated, the probability was above 90% in the condition of 90% confidence level and 0.15 one-way deviation allowance.
- The impact location error of damage events was less than 20% with $\alpha=0.1$ as significance level.
- This study could give reference for the further research of complicated airplane structure damage monitoring and location based on Acoustic Emission.

However, the above conclusions are feasible for specific structure under certain conditions. In actual monitoring, the AE signal collected by the equipment should be sure in active condition for different structures. Set reasonable sound velocity, and then refer to this article to finish damage monitoring.

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